

Employees' Perception Analysis towards Leadership Effectiveness Competencies in Indian Manufacturing Industries

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Abstract—The purpose of this research paper on the subject of Leadership Effectiveness attempts to conduct a focused amount of research to examine the employees' perceptions pertaining to specific competencies of leadership effectiveness in Indian manufacturing industries and to correlate their perceptions between private sectors and public sector undertakings. It specifically looks at the current definitions of leadership and looks at some historical background information relating to the more common theories that relate to leadership and effectiveness. This research was conducted by using a variety of current books and periodical articles on the topic of leadership effectiveness and employees' perceptions. A number of leadership effectiveness competencies have been identified. The demographic details and perception of the employees on importance of leadership effectiveness competencies have been obtained through a well designed online questionnaire. For this purpose, a likert scale of seven-point has been used. Descriptive and inferential statistics is used to analyze the gathered data.

Keywords—Employees Perception, Leadership Effectiveness, Leadership Competencies, Manufacturing.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE present research paper is focused about leadership with its main objective to analyze and outline what leadership is, in the context of the 21st century. It takes on the following questions: How has leadership changed during the past years? What are the most critical components in leadership? What are the key leadership effectiveness competencies? How can we ourselves become and develop better leaders for the future?

The availability of the literature and the extensive research work being done at present clearly indicates that leadership will once again emerge as one of the pivotal areas in the years to come. Today, we had already started experiencing a clear lack of good leadership in our organizations. There exists a strong correlation between good leadership and the performance of the organization and hence it has become an emerging and thrust area of much research and debate. In the

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past decade, we had focused mainly on product and process management, re-engineering, quality, organizational culture and learning. Having implemented all of these, we had observed lack of 'something else' as is evident from the functioning and performance of the organizations. Many a time the missing link is true leadership. There seems to be a lack of intelligent leaders, who are able to create and sustain an inspiring vision and implement the vision together with their teams. Thus it becomes more significant to analyze different leadership effectiveness competencies and how the employee's of an organization perceive about these competencies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

An organization is a social set up which has a boundary [1]. This boundary separates it from its environment, pursues its own collective goals, and controls its performance. The interactions are rationally coordinated and directed through time on a continuous basis in any formal organization. The person at the helm of affairs is usually the leader. Though, word leadership is very common and widely used by most disciplines: politicians; social workers, business executives and educationists, yet no exact definition of leadership exist and the researches have large disagreement as regards the exact meaning of leadership.

Leadership can be defined as, "leadership is getting people to do things they have never thought of doing, do not believe are possible or that they do not want to do", and in reference to an organization as "the action of committing employees to contribute their best to the purpose of the organization", [2]. Leadership depends on characteristics, personal abilities of an individual as well as of the situation and environment [3].

History has witnessed the critical roles played by leaders and leadership in any organizational (business endeavor, educational institutions, military force or any other group of diverse individuals, working toward common goals) success. Effective leadership is a fundamental truth in all walks of life, public and private and any organization must create focus and commitment on the part of its members irrespective of its nature or orientation. One should always consider the people first, treat them well, and place paramount importance on their welfare, morale and the opportunity to grow and excel as the effective leadership begins with people.

III. DEFINITIONS OF LEADERSHIP

Leadership is like beauty; it is hard to define, but you know it when you see it [4]. There are hundreds of definitions about leadership, but it is very difficult to either define its exact meaning or to find any widely accepted definition among leadership theorists [5], [6]. Some definitions are given below:

- Leadership is the reciprocal process of mobilizing by persons with certain motives and values, various economic, political and other resources, in context of competition and conflict, in order to realize goals independently or mutually held by both leaders and followers [7].
- Leadership is a process of influencing one or more people in a positive way so that the tasks determined by the goals and objectives of an organization are accomplished [8].
- Leadership refers to interpersonal processes in social groups, through which some individuals assist and direct the group toward the completion of group goals [9].
- A review of other writers reveals that most management writers agree that leadership is the process of influencing the activities of an individual or a group in efforts towards goal achievement in a given situation [10].
- Leadership is a process and a property. The process of leadership is the use of non-coercive influence to direct and coordinate the activities of the members of an organized group toward the accomplishment of group objectives. As a property, leadership is a set of qualities or characteristics attributed to those who are perceived to successfully employ such influence [11].
- Leadership has been defined in many ways. The most consistent element noted is that leadership involves the process of influence between a leader and followers to attain group, organizational or societal goals [12].
- Leadership is an influence relationship among leaders and followers who intend real changes that reflect their mutual purposes [6].
- Leadership is an activity or set of activities, observable to others, that occurs in group, organization, or institution and which involves a leader and followers who willingly subscribe to common purposes and work together to achieve them [13].
- Leadership is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal [14].
- Leadership behavior is purposeful interaction among humans that takes place in a certain group. The interaction has to be such that it improves the performance of the group and maintains constant development in relation to solving surfacing problems and achieving set goals. Leadership behavior is based on the personal potential of a leader and its efficiency is affected by the operational environment, situational factors and the goals set for activities [15].

IV. HISTORY AND PERTINENCE OF LEADERSHIP MODELS

The scientific study of leadership can be roughly divided

into periods: the trait period, from around 1910 to World War II, the behavior period, from the onset of World War II to the late 1960s, and the contingency period, from the late 1960s to the present [16]. The most recent models of leadership that have evolved are those dealing with transformation and strategic vision and are often referred to as the leader and follower schools of thought [17]. The objective here is to analyze the previous leadership theories and learn to know, how they are trying to explain the leadership phenomenon from their own perspective. There are numerous leadership theories; in only the past 50 years, there have been as many as 65 different classifications of leadership dimensions [18]. In this research paper, the different models and theories have been grouped into the following 20 groups:

1. Ancient approaches
2. Classical approaches
3. Behavior and style theories
4. Situational Leadership Theory
5. Unified leadership
6. Management by objectives
7. Shared leadership
8. Sacrificial or Servant Leadership Model
9. Greatness Theory
10. Transformational and Transactional Leadership
11. Genetic Leadership Theory
12. Trait Theory
13. Contingency Theory
14. Normative Leadership Model
15. Path-Goal Theory Model
16. Leader-member exchange theory
17. Team leadership
18. Self-leadership
19. Relational leadership
20. Emotional intelligence

The details of these theories/models are available in open literature and it can be well established that the leadership phenomenon can be approached from many different perspectives. These twenty groups don't include all leadership theories or approaches, however, it is believed that the theories and approaches belonging to these twenty groups give a quite comprehensive picture of the situation. The literature reveals that the theories/models presently in practice have been developed mainly during the sixties and seventies and transformational leadership by [7] may be the last true invention. The working environment of leaders has changed dramatically thus emotional and spiritual components need to be added to our rational thinking. There is a need to integrate the best features of old approaches and even use parts of them, which are still valid.

V. CORPORATE LEADERSHIP

Recent researches on corporate leadership indicated that most of the organizations in the world are experiencing some sort of "leadership gap" within their executives with current leadership benches deemed inadequate either in number or in

qualifications. The inadequate leadership talent costs the organizations seriously and hence the organizations are looking for individuals who possess competencies beyond technical skills to fill this gap.

In 1977, the Corporate Leadership Council, partnered with Boston, Massachusetts-based Cambria Consulting, and analyzed leadership competency models from over 50 companies, revealing similar leadership competency models, which stressed non-technical competencies for leaders. Based on this analysis, they identified the following top ten corporate leadership competencies:

1. Drive for Results
2. People Development
3. Conceptual Grasp/Big Picture Awareness
4. Team Player
5. Flexibility
6. Integrity/Honesty
7. Learning Orientation
8. Strategic Thinking
9. Setting of Vision and Direction
10. Creation of High-Performance Climate

VI. LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS

Leadership effectiveness is summarized in major findings of significant studies dealing with different leadership behaviors and strategies for increasing leadership effectiveness. Leader's effectiveness is determined by how well his leadership style fits the specific situation [19]. It was further used to analyze the impact of experience and training on leadership effectiveness with a focus on the leadership behaviors of "initiating structure" and "consideration".

It was concluded that the quality of problem-solving decisions made by a group of individuals is consistently better than that of individuals and compared group members' reactions to three types of participative decision-making. It was demonstrated that the success of participative decision-making depends on the method of governance used. It may be inferred that leadership needs vary with different situations and there are no absolute guidelines for leadership effectiveness.

The helpfulness of constructive and developmental theory in studying effective leadership grounded in social science research conducted by Piaget, Kohlberg, Perry, and others, has four stages. In the imperial stage, the individual's frames of reference are personal goals and agendas. At the interpersonal stage, individuals can reflect on others' interests, experience, trust and commitment. Persons in the institutional stage have developed a subjective frame of reference allowing for self-definition in terms of internal values and standards, not merely connections to others. In inter-individual stage, end values have become the object and a "global" worldview becomes the organizing process.

It was emphasized that ambition is the only inherent character trait needed for leadership effectiveness and other competencies of leadership effectiveness can be learned [20].

Further, stated that an understanding of how individuals and groups of individuals construct their notions of effective leadership within complex organizations must be developed to determine effectiveness of those in leadership positions accurately and fairly.

Leadership effectiveness is an outcome of leader's behavior rather than a particular type of behavior [21]. Reference [22] measured leadership effectiveness using numerous indicators such as follower's attitudes, level of commitment given to the organization, motivation towards the job, performance and outcomes of the organization and of group productivity. However this is contrary with the views of [23] which indicates that effective leadership contains five categories namely team performance, integrity, trustworthiness, performance in venues, self rating and concluded that key to leader's effectiveness is ability to build a team.

VII. LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS COMPETENCIES

There are certain basic qualities or characteristics that most people associate with leadership. Some of these include self-confidence, independent, assertive, decision maker, dominant, trustworthiness, and team player, etc. and the person who posses these attributes are often labeled as —leaders. An effective leader is someone who motivates a person or a group to accomplish more than they would have otherwise accomplished without that leader's involvement. We can relate this to the sporting arena where a team is comprised of individual players; each with certain competencies, but the team is honed into a finely tuned instrument by virtue of the coach orchestrating them into a cohesive unit. In this manner, and only with the proper motivation and care, will this group of individuals gel into a team and accomplish more together than they ever could on their own merits. With this framework set in place, it can be well argued that there are many leadership effectiveness competencies to be effective leader.

After researching many references on this topic, and reading many of the empirical data available on leadership effectiveness competencies, it is found that there is still ample opportunity for research and case studies in this area of leadership effectiveness competencies and employees' perception about it. Further, there is no such case study is available on employees' perception towards leadership effectiveness competencies in Indian manufacturing industries. Therefore, we must come up with some definitive facts on the key ingredients of leadership effectiveness i.e. competencies and analyze whether employees sex, age, social status, qualification and experience, etc. plays a pivotal role in this.

VIII. CONCEPT OF PERCEPTION

Perception is an important aspect to be studied because people's behavior is based on their perception of what reality is not on reality itself [24]. Perception is the mental process of observing the outer physical world and processing that information into patterns meaningful to the brain [25].

Perception was also defined as what ones perceive can be substantially different from objective reality. Perceptions are fundamental to our forming options about our-selves.

TABLE I
 SAMPLE DEMOGRAPHY

Particulars	Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	%age
Age			
21-30 years	26	26	25.24
31-40 years	37	63	35.92
41-50 years	25	88	24.27
51-60 years	14	102	13.59
above 60 years	1	103	0.97
Education Level			
Undergraduate	23	23	22.33
Postgraduate	62	85	60.19
Doctorate Degree	4	89	3.88
Any other	14	103	13.59
Gender			
Male	100	100	97.09
Female	3	103	2.91
Job Tenure (Experience)			
0 – 5 years	17	17	16.50
5 – 10 years	24	41	23.30
10 – 15 years	21	62	20.39
> 15 years	41	103	39.81
Seniority (Current Social Status)			
Lower Level Management	20	20	19.42
Middle level Management	47	67	45.63
Upper Level Management	27	94	26.21
Top level Management	9	103	8.74

IX. RESEARCH DESIGN

Participant: The sample was one of convenience: It has been randomly selected 103 executives involving 10 organizations, encompassing medium and large size ones. These were manufacturing companies in the fields of consumer electronics, automobiles, laboratory equipments and electricity generation etc. These manufacturing organizations are mainly divided into two groups – private sector and public sector undertakings. The executives are the citizens of India. The participation was voluntary. The sample, stratified according to age, gender, job tenure (experience), education level and seniority (current social status), is presented in Table I.

Fig. 1 Sample demography

The sample was believed to be fairly representative of the demographic profile of the organizations. From Table I, it is apparent that the sample consisted of mostly males than females (approximately 97% versus 3%, respectively). As this study was conducted in manufacturing organizations and only the executives were involved thus the majority of the participants had relatively high level of education (~60% postgraduate). Considering the length of time that the participants had been working in the organizations, it would therefore be fair to presume that the participants knew their organizations and well enough to answer the questions. The same explanation could further be responsible for seniority as majority of the participants are working at middle level management (45%). These details, who completed the survey, are also presented in Fig. 1.

Measuring Instruments: The instrument used in this research is a well designed questionnaire to collect the data in accordance to the questionnaire developed. Likert scale questionnaire is suitable to gather data from large group of participants. Basically the participants will easy to understand and answer the Likert scale questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of two sections. Section-A measured the demographic data of the participants. Section-B measured the level of importance for various leadership effectiveness competencies on a predetermined seven-point scale: Extremely Important; Very-Very Important; Very Important; Important; Somewhat Important; Less Important and Not Important. The questionnaire was prepared online on google document and the participants were approached to reply online. Section B of the questionnaire was related to 13 leadership effectiveness competencies consisting of 77 leadership effectiveness sub-competencies. The competencies are given in Table II.

Statistical Analysis: All statistical analyses were based on the assumption that the sample (N=103) was drawn from a normally distributed population. This was a reasonable assumption, given that a sample size of 25 or 30 is generally considered sufficiently large for most situations.

Reliability Test: Reliability test was done to test the reliability of all leadership effectiveness competencies. The results of the reliability test are given in Table III.

In this research paper, Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.768 to 0.887 were found for the different leadership competencies. These coefficients are acceptable and the reliability for the combinations of the competencies is higher (0.962). Any value greater than 0.6 is considered good. These test results show that there are consistencies and stability of the answers from the participants. The information gathered from the participants is analyzed by the Statistics Package for Social Science, version 17 (SPSS) through descriptive statistics and inferential statistics to analyze and measure the differences of perception between two variables and to examine the strength of the relationship between independent and dependent variables.

X.RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Hypothesis - 1: There is no difference between perceptions of the employees of different age group and leadership effectiveness competencies.

Hypothesis - 2: There is no difference between perceptions of the employees of different education level and leadership effectiveness competencies.

Hypothesis - 3: There is no difference between perceptions of the employees of different gender and leadership effectiveness competencies.

TABLE II
 LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS COMPETENCIES

S. No.	Leadership Effectiveness Competency	S. No.	Leadership Effectiveness Competency
1	Decision Making	8	Persuading
2	Self Motivation	9	Change Management
3	Use of Technology	10	Emotional Intelligence
4	Problem Solving	11	Inspiration
5	Planning and Organizing	12	People Management
6	Communication skills	13	General Personality
7	Knowledge Management		

TABLE III
 RELIABILITIES OF LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS COMPETENCIES

S. No.	Leadership Effectiveness Competency	Valid Case		Cronbach's' Alpha
		N	%age	
1	Decision Making	103	100	.769
2	Self Motivation	103	100	.782
3	Use of Technology	103	100	.805
4	Problem Solving	103	100	.819
5	Planning and Organizing	103	100	.814
6	Communication skills	103	100	.841
7	Knowledge Management	103	100	.768
8	Persuading	103	100	.829
9	Change Management	103	100	.887
10	Emotional Intelligence	103	100	.711
11	Inspiration	103	100	.787
12	People Management	103	100	.880
13	General Personality	103	100	.765
14	Overall Competencies	103	100	.962

Hypothesis - 4: There is no difference between perceptions of the employees of different job tenure (experience) and leadership effectiveness competencies.

Hypothesis - 5: There is no difference between perceptions of the employees of different seniority (current social status) and leadership effectiveness competencies.

Hypothesis - 6: There is no difference between perceptions of the employees of different industries (private and public sectors) and leadership effectiveness competencies.

The descriptive statistics of the various measures reveals that the minimum importance of any leadership effectiveness competency on a predetermined seven-point scale is 4.75 and the maximum importance is 6.037 for any category of employee consisting of various groups based on their demographic factors. The average importance of any leadership effectiveness competency for the whole

participants lies between 5.468 and 5.864. It is concluded that all leadership effectiveness competencies are equally important for Indian manufacturing industries.

In order to establish whether there is any difference between perceptions of the employees based on their demographic factors and leadership effectiveness competencies, analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests were performed. The results of the test are shown in Tables IV and V. The results of the tests indicate that there is no difference in the importance of leadership effectiveness competencies based on demographic factors of the employees as the value of $P > 0.05$ in all cases except in case of 'self motivation' based on job tenure (Experience) where it is 0.023. Therefore, the hypotheses 1 to 6 are substantiated.

Table VI presents the results of the inter-correlation matrix. Significant correlations were obtained between the leadership effectiveness competencies. The value of correlation lies between 0.514 and 0.825. The results show that all leadership effectiveness competencies are correlated positively with affective commitment.

TABLE IV
INFERENCE STATISTICS (ANOVA) OF LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS
COMPETENCIES BASED ON DEMOGRAPHY OF EMPLOYEES

Leadership Effectiveness Competency	Seniority (Current Social Status)		Job Tenure (Experience)		Age Group	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
	Decision Making	.963	.413	.760	.519	.773
Self Motivation	2.12	.102	3.304	.023	.965	.430
Use of Technology	.458	.712	1.197	.315	.273	.895
Problem Solving	.951	.419	1.033	.382	.583	.676
Planning and Organizing	.499	.684	1.143	.336	.186	.945
Communication skills	.391	.760	1.819	.149	.496	.739
Knowledge Management	.429	.732	2.657	.053	.241	.915
Persuading	.507	.678	.578	.631	.506	.732
Change Management	.901	.443	1.314	.274	.412	.800
Emotional Intelligence	.519	.670	.295	.829	.200	.938
Inspiration	.276	.843	1.020	.387	.653	.626
People Management	.551	.648	.120	.948	.215	.930
General Personality	.182	.909	.335	.800	.179	.949

TABLE V
INFERENCE STATISTICS (ANOVA) OF LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS
COMPETENCIES BASED ON DEMOGRAPHY OF EMPLOYEES

Leadership Effectiveness Competency	Gender		Industry Type		Education Level	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
Decision Making	.459	.500	.463	.498	.462	.709
Self Motivation	1.171	.282	.375	.542	.308	.819
Use of Technology	.066	.798	1.214	.273	.107	.956
Problem Solving	.541	.464	1.860	.176	.217	.885
Planning and Organizing	.903	.344	1.076	.302	.061	.980
Communication skills	2.200	.141	.221	.639	.603	.614
Knowledge Management	.101	.752	.007	.933	1.81	.150
Persuading	.129	.720	.998	.320	1.02	.384
Change Management	1.156	.285	.000	.994	.919	.434
Emotional Intelligence	.247	.620	.595	.442	.329	.804
Inspiration	.001	.971	.069	.793	1.48	.223
People Management	.002	.961	.023	.880	1.40	.247
General Personality	.437	.510	.639	.426	.843	.474

TABLE VI
RELIABILITIES OF LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS COMPETENCIES

Leadership Effectiveness Competency	Decision Making	Self Motivation	Use of Technology	Problem Solving	Planning and Organizing	Communication skills	Knowledge Management	Persuading	Change Management	Emotional Intelligence	Inspiration	People Management	General Personality
Decision Making	1												
Self Motivation	.666	1											
Use of Technology	.609	.621	1										
Problem Solving	.629	.595	.662	1									
Planning and Organizing	.705	.685	.693	.708	1								
Communication skills	.723	.735	.672	.734	.719	1							
Knowledge Management	.605	.600	.619	.660	.654	.732	1						
Persuading	.605	.537	.518	.629	.564	.670	.668	1					
Change Management	.722	.692	.644	.712	.745	.825	.802	.759	1				
Emotional Intelligence	.658	.652	.560	.615	.616	.729	.626	.601	.763	1			
Inspiration	.655	.588	.598	.635	.784	.671	.678	.661	.738	.640	1		
People Management	.671	.637	.705	.772	.743	.744	.689	.674	.805	.652	.729	1	
General Personality	.576	.514	.588	.688	.666	.674	.647	.604	.705	.550	.651	.752	1

XI. CONCLUSIONS

The research work was an exploratory attempt to test an integrated model consisting of thirteen leadership effectiveness competencies - Decision Making; Self Motivation; Use of Technology; Problem Solving; Planning and Organizing; Communication skills; Knowledge Management; Persuading; Change Management; Emotional Intelligence; Inspiration; People Management; and General Personality. In particular, the objective of the study was to investigate the relationships between perceptions of the employees based on their demographic factors and leadership effectiveness competencies. The findings show that there is no difference between the demographic factors (education level, job tenure – experience, seniority – current social status, gender, age group) in perceiving leadership effectiveness competencies. Further the research indicates that the employees of private sector and public sector undertakings perceive the leadership effectiveness competencies in a similar manner. It is also well established that all leadership effectiveness competencies are positively correlated and are of equal importance in context of Indian manufacturing industries. In summary, this study makes a contribution to our knowledge of leadership effectiveness in that it evaluates the relationships between perception of employees and leadership effectiveness competencies.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hicks, G. H. And Gullet, C. R. Organizations Theory and Behaviour, NY: McGraw-Hill, 1975, pp 245 - 59.
- [2] Taffinder, Paul. 2006. Leadership Crash Course: How to create Personal Leadership Value (2nd Ed.) London, GBR: Kogan Page Limited (pp 6).
- [3] Messick D. Mand Kramer R. M. Psychology of Leadership: some new approach. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Incorporated, 2004.
- [4] Bennis, W. On Becoming a Leader. Perseus Books. Cambridge. Massachusetts, 1989.
- [5] Bass, B.M. Bass and Stogdill's Handbook of Leadership. Theory, Research and Managerial Applications. Third Edition. The Free Press. New York, 1990.
- [6] Rost, J.C. Leadership for the Twenty-First Century. (First published 1991) Praeger. Westport, 1993.
- [7] Burns, J.M. Leadership. Harper & Row. New York, 1978.
- [8] Hart, L.B. Moving up! Women and Leadership. AMACOM. NY, 1980.
- [9] Segal, D.R. Leadership and Management: Organizational Theory. In R.H. Ruch & L.J. Korb (Eds.) Military Leadership, 41-69. Sage. Beverly Hills, 1981.
- [10] Hersey, Paul & Blanchard, Ken. Management of Organizational Behavior. Utilizing Human Resources. 4th ed. Prentice-Hall, Inc. Englewood Cliffs, 1982.
- [11] Jago, A.G. Leadership: Perspectives in Theory and Research. Management Science, Vol. 28, 1982, pp 315-336. Hollander, E. P. Leadership and Power. In G. Lindzey & E. Aronson (Eds.): Handbook of Social Psychology, 1985, pp 485-537. Random House. New York.
- [12] Clarke, K. & Clarke, M. Choosing to Lead. CLL. Leadership Press. Richmond, 1996.
- [13] Northhouse, Peter G. Leadership: Theory and Practice. Sage Publications, Inc., Thousand Oaks, 2001.
- [14] Nissinen, V. Military Leadership. A Critical Constructivist Approach to Conceptualizing, Modelling and Measuring Military Leadership in the Finnish Defence Forces. Academic Dissertation. National Defence College, 2001.
- [15] Chemers, M M. Leadership Research and Theory: A Functional Integration. Journal of Applied Social Psychology. Vol. 4, 2000, pp 27-43.
- [16] Greenberg, Jerald, Managing Behaviour in Organizations, Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ, 1999.
- [17] Fleishman, E. A. & Mumford, M.D.& Zaccaro, S. J. & Lewin, K. Y. & Korotkin, A. L. & Hein, M. B. 1991. Taxonomic Efforts in the Descriptions of Leader Behavior: A Synthesis and Functional Interpretation. Leadership Quarterly, 2(4), 245-287.
- [18] Fiedler, F. F. A Theory of Leadership Effectiveness. McGraw-Hill. New York, 1967.
- [19] O'Toole, J. Leadership A to Z: A guide for the Appropriately Ambitious. San Francisco, Jossey-Bass, 1999.
- [20] Jogulu, U.D. & Wood, G. J. The role of Leadership Theory in Raising the Profile of Women in Management. Equal Opportunities

International. Vol. 25, 2006, pp 236-250.

- [21] Howell, D. C. Statistical Methods for psychology (5th Ed.), USA, Duxbury, 2002.
- [22] Hopkins, M.M., O'Neil, D.A. & Bilimoria, D. Effective Leadership and Successful Career Advancement: Perspectives from Women in Health Care. Equal Opportunities International. Vol. 25, 2006, pp 251-271.
- [23] Robbins, S.P. & Judge, T.A. Organizational Behavior. 12th Ed. New Jersey; Pearson Prentice Hall, 2007.
- [24] Fritz, S., Hannan, E., Smith K.G., Turner, T., Wert, M. & Dawson, J. Chief Executive Leadership Styles, Consensus Decision Making and Top Management Effectiveness. European Journal of Work and Organization Psychology. Vol. 9, 2007, pp 401-420.
- [25] Zaidatun Tasir & Mohd Salleh Abu. Analisis Data Berkomputer: SPSS 11.5 for windows. Venton publishing; Kuala Lumpur, 2003.

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